

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE MUSIC CULTURE LESSON

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Abstract. This article discusses music culture and its effectiveness.

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It is no coincidence that the question of what the object, subject, goals and objectives of advanced pedagogical technologies are, what results their application to the educational process gives and what impact it has on improving the content of education is raised in the teaching of each subject. The incredibly rapid and intense development of science, technology and information transfer and exchange technologies, in turn, requires the enrichment of traditional methods with new modern and interactive methods in the field of education. So, in what aspects do interactive, modeled methods have an advantage?

It is necessary for every student-mentor and educator to be ready to answer the questions of what its types, structural structure, forms and means of organizing educational processes are, how it differs from previously existing teaching (Education) methods, what its effectiveness is proven by, and how its monitoring and evaluation system is carried out. This is the most important social task facing them, and it is necessary for them to understand and answer these questions. No matter how much the State Educational Standards, which are the main normative and programmatic documents for implementing the tasks set out in the Law "On Education" and the "National Program for Personnel Training", reflect the requirements for the content and level of education, the curriculum, model subject programs, new generation textbooks, teaching methods, and the latest achievements in science and education, and no matter how much the educational process and its organization are strengthened and modernized, the final result ultimately depends on the professional knowledge, skills, creativity, initiative, pedagogical skills and intellectual potential of the teachers and trainers who organize the educational process, ensure the content and quality of the lesson, and their ability to interest students in acquiring knowledge in the subject, and to realize the most necessary aspirational abilities. will remain.

It is worth noting that ensuring the quality and effectiveness of education and upbringing is a matter of the correct, meaningful, and interesting organization of the educational process aimed at the mastering of the educational content by the student, in which the student becomes not just a simple listener in the lesson, but an active participant in the lesson, an independent task-performer, an independent and creative thinker, an active person who can freely express his or her opinions and defend his or her opinions. It is clear that such an organization of the educational process requires, first of all, to be taken into account in the process of preparing future teachers for the profession in higher education institutions. Therefore, professors and teachers working in higher education should conduct training in the subject they teach in a technologically advanced form and prepare their students for this activity. Studying, observing and analyzing practical experiences in the application of pedagogical technologies in education shows that organizing classes based on interactive methods is becoming widespread in almost all areas of education. In our opinion, this should not lead to the conclusion that one or another type of pedagogical technology should be used in every

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lesson. In music lessons, most students imitate the teacher, follow him, take a role model, the teacher's personal "example" is of great importance.

Because practical performance takes a leading place in the lesson, no goals can be achieved with a dry narrative style. Well-organized scientific and pedagogical training is one of the main factors ensuring the effectiveness of education. Teachers who actively participate in this process regularly improve their pedagogical skills and serve as an example to others in ensuring the effectiveness of education and upbringing, in bringing up a responsible and harmonious generation for the future. Therefore, good results can be achieved by constantly improving and encouraging the innovative activities and experiences of advanced teachers who teach "Music Culture" classes at every level of education, including in secondary schools.

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